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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE ENFORCEABILITY OF CONTRACT OF RESTRAINT IN TRADE

By

HABILA ISAH BARAU*, IBOME HABILA BULMEN**

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on contracts in restraint of trade in employment. Public policy demands that every person should be at liberty to work for himself and shall not be at liberty to deny himself or his state of labour, skill, or talent by any agreement that he enters into. This work examined instances where such liberty is restrained by contracts made in restraint of trade and also went further to look at whether such contracts are only aimed at protecting the employer or both the employer and the employee, with the aim of giving a clearer understanding of the subject matter of this research and to equally create a pathway to further research. This work used the doctrinal method of research as the sources of materials are library based and no form of non-doctrinal research was resorted to. The main limitation to this study was the availability of recent judicial authorities in respect to this subject matter as a lot of jurisdictions have moved a step further by adopting Competition Laws in their Countries, while in Nigeria where the competition laws though enacted, have not been made effective and people rarely resort to court to settle such issues. The study recommends the need to empower the newly established Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission to be more effective by amending the Act in tune with international best practice.

Keywords: Enforceability, Contract, Restraint, Trade

1. INTRODUCTION

Employers often dread losing key staff. The difficulty involved in having to recruit and successfully integrate new faces into an existing order makes the endeavor an unsavory undertaking to many. However, if losing a key staff is worrisome enough, the realization that a disgruntled one may walk out the door with more than his termination letter and severance paycheck, is a much graver cause for concern. Daily, employers are faced with the unfortunate reality that a departing employee may leave to go work with a competitor, poach their long-term clients or utilize skills, confidential information and trade secrets acquired during the subsistence of their employment to secure new jobs. This apprehension has prompted many employers to have prospective employees sign non-compete agreements as a prerequisite for working for them. The position of restrictive covenants in Nigeria is similar to that in England; there is no express prohibition of restrictive covenants under employment laws in Nigeria.

In this work, our discussion will be focused on the covenants in restraint of trade, the ingredients for the test of validity, the applicability of such covenants in certain trade environments, remedies for breach of restrictive covenants, jurisdiction of Courts in respect of matters relating to such covenants, conclusion, and recommendations all with the aim of deciphering which party to the contract is favored by such covenants. This will be done by looking at relevant literature and case laws in this regard. It is important to note that there are only two things an employer can protect:

- (a) Trade secrets; and
- (b) Business connection

A restraint against competition is justifiable if its object is to prevent the exploitation of trade secrets learned by the employee in the course of his employment. In this connection, it should be noted that the area of the restraint must not be excessive. Furthermore, a restraint under this heading may be invalid because its duration is excessive.¹Sometimes an employer may use a covenant against solicitation of persons with whom the employer does business to protect his business connection. The

¹ Denis Keenan, *Smith & Keenan's Advanced Business Law* (10th edn. Pitman publishing 1997)169. See also *Forster & Sons Ltd v Suggett* (1918) 35 TLR 87

problem of area is less important in this type of covenant (to protect business connection), though its duration must be reasonable. The burden on the employer increases as the duration of the restraint is extended, though in rare situations a restraint for life may be valid.²

At this point it is pertinent to give clarification of certain terms which will form the bedrock of our discussion.

2. CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION OF TERMS

i. Restrictive Covenants

This is a contract in which a party agrees to be restricted in some regards as to future conduct.³ A contract in restraint of trade is one which contains a provision by which one of the parties agrees to suffer a restriction with regard to the carrying on of his trade or profession.⁴ It may be a contract by which both parties agree to suffer restriction in the way they carry on business.⁵ A restrictive covenant is typically a clause in a contract which **prohibits an employee from competing** with his ex-employer for a certain period after the employee has left the business, or **prevents the ex-employee from soliciting or dealing with customers** of the business by using knowledge of those customers gained during his prior employment.⁶

Types of Restrictive Covenants

The standard types of restrictions which can be used by employers are:

- **non-competition covenants** - restrictions on the former employee working in similar employment for a competitor;
- **non-solicitation covenants** – which prevent poaching of clients/customers/suppliers of the former employer;

² Ibid

³ Duhaime's Law Dictionary 'Restrictive Covenant Definition' www.duhaime.org/LegalDictionary/R/RestrictiveCovenant.aspx accessed on 1/6/2024

⁴ W. T Major *Casebook on Contract Law* (Pitman) 187

⁵ Ibid

⁶ Pinsent Masons 'Restrictive covenants in employment contracts' <https://www.out-law.com/page-7086> accessed on 1/6/2024

- **non-dealing covenants** – which prevent a former employee from dealing with former clients/customers/suppliers, regardless of which party approached the other;
- **Non-poaching covenants** – which prevent an employee poaching former colleagues.

ii. EMPLOYMENT CONTRACTS

An Employment Contract is a legal document that outlines the terms of employment between an employer and an employee. It usually makes provisions for such terms as Names of the Employer and Employee, Starting Date of Employment, Address of Employment, Job Title and Description of Employment Duties, Salary, Expenses, Hours Worked Each Week, Time off Work, Pension Details, Probationary Period, Performance Assessments, Terms of Employment, Deductions, Confidentiality/Restrictive Covenants, Grievances, and Notice for Termination of Contract et cetera.⁷

1.0 HISTORY OF RESTRICTIVE COVENANTS IN TRADE

The history of restrictive covenant law dates back to the apprenticeship system in pre-industrial England. In the earliest cases, masters had attempted to prevent competition from their apprentices following the apprenticeship period, through the use of agreements not to practice for a set period of time. British courts uniformly struck down such agreements as against public policy, arguing that enforced idleness is detrimental to both the individual apprentice and the society.⁸ In the famous *Dyer's Case*,⁹ the court held that the apprentice's covenant not to practice his trade in London for 2 years following his apprenticeship was void regardless of its terms. Given that the apprentice was trained only in a single particular skill and had limited mobility, the court determined that a restrictive covenant violated his right to livelihood and constituted a wrongful attempt to prolong subservience.

⁷ 'What is a Nigerian Employment Agreement or Employee/Employer work agreement' <https://www.documatica-forms.com/nigeria/employment-agreement/more-info.php> accessed on 1/6/2024

⁸ Hoguet Newman Regal & Kenney, Brief History of Restrictive Covenant Law <http://blog.hnrklaw.com/brief-history-of-restrictive-covenant-law/> accessed on 18/5/2024

⁹ (1414) 2 Hen. V, fol. 5, pl. 26

The current legal framework for enforcing restrictive covenants found its origin in the case of *Mitchel v. Reynolds*¹⁰ a few centuries after *Dyer's* case, in which a London baker leased his bakery and agreed not to compete locally but later broke that promise. At trial, the baker argued that this covenant was an illegal restraint on his livelihood that could not be enforced. Despite declaring that restrictive covenants are disfavored (“the law presumes them bad”), the court applied a rule of reason to uphold the agreement. The court based its reasonableness determination on a few factors, particularly:

- (1) That the covenant was supported by adequate consideration,
- (2) That the restraint was limited rather than general in nature, and
- (3) That the public was not unduly injured by the restraint.

Furthermore, the court distinguished this covenant for the transfer of business from covenants between employers and employees, noting that in a business transfer, the parties are more likely to negotiate as equals and mutually benefit from the restraint. In making this distinction, the court reaffirmed judicial skepticism of covenants between an employer/master and an employee/apprentice, which may be prone to “great abuses... from masters, who are apt to give their apprentices much vexation on this account, and to use many indirect practices to procure such bonds from them, lest they should prejudice them in their custom, when they come up to set up for themselves.”¹¹

American courts adopted this precedent and almost universally rejected restrictive covenants throughout the 1800s. Employer attempts to restrain competition in New York were denied without regard to circumstance. Unlike 19th century British courts, which placed an increasing emphasis on freedom of contract to eliminate the traditional presumption against restrictive covenants, U.S. courts emphasized employee protection from exploitation, safeguarding the right to earn a living, and defending the public from loss of a free market. Their rejection of restrictive covenants applied not only to labor constraints but also to constraints on the flow of information.

¹⁰ (1711) 24 ER 347

¹¹ *Hoguet & Kenney*(n 6)

If an employee acquires knowledge on a job, the employer could not limit any subsequent use of that knowledge, in the absence of protection by patent.¹²

This broad rejection of restrictive covenants began to wane around 1900 as courts started recognizing internal business information such as knowledge of particular customers and strategies as warranting legal protection. For the first time, U.S. courts identified a legitimate employer interest in restricting employee competition in order to prevent the abuse of confidences and protect employer investments. Quickly, the American and British approaches became largely aligned. The rule of reason set forth in *Mitchel v. Reynolds*¹³ was adapted for modern times, with the British House of Lords and the American Restatement of Contracts (1932) espousing similar standards to enforce restrictive covenants, including most importantly that the restraint be no greater than necessary to reasonably protect the employer's legitimate interests. As expressed in the 1932 Restatement of Contracts and then echoed by the 1979 edition, a restrictive covenant is reasonable if it;

- (1) is no greater than required for protection of the employer,
- (2) Imposes no undue hardship on the employee, and
- (3) Tends not to substantially harm the public interest.

Though Courts continue to refine and revise conceptions of the permissible duration and scope of a restrictive covenant to afford reasonable protection, the essential standard for enforceability remains unchanged.¹⁴ It is pertinent to note that restrictive covenant is a precursor to competition law.

4.0 COVENANTS IN RESTRAINT OF TRADE

The Common law protects an employer during the subsistence of a contract of employment, since one incidence of an implied term of good faith is that the employee should not compete with his employer.¹⁵ This includes a prohibition against canvassing

¹² Ibid

¹³ (1711)1 PWms 181

¹⁴ Ibid

¹⁵ Titman & Camp *Individual Employment Law* (3rd Edn. Sweet & Maxwell, 1989)20

the employer's customers.¹⁶This rule applies even to the last day at work and sometimes a reasonable period after the contract of employment has ended.

A distinction must always be drawn between the duty owed by an employee during the subsistence of the contract of employment, and the duty owed after the employment has terminated. In the former case, the duty is contractual, whether as an express or implied term of the contract of employment. This means that an employee cannot improperly disclose information or give any assistance to a competitor, even if this is in his own time. The duty of loyalty of an employee to his employer during the course of an employment was adequately captured in the case of *HIVAC LTD v PARK ROYAL SCIENTIFIC INSTRUMENTS LTD*¹⁷ where the employees, who were skilled workers, were employed by a company making hearing aids and in their spare time worked for a direct competitor, and also persuaded other employees of the employer to work for the competitor on a part-time basis. Although no confidential information was passed on by the part-time employees, the Plaintiffs were granted an interlocutory injunction to prevent the Defendants (the part-time employers) from employing the employees of the employer on this basis. It was said that in assessing the duty of the employees in such cases, all circumstances had to be looked at, but the employees had deliberately set themselves on a course which would harm their employers and so were in breach of this duty of loyalty to them.¹⁸The obligations of an ex-employee are more limited; he may be under duty not to disclose information which has been imparted to him in confidence, and he may be restrained from working for a competitor by a validly worded restricted covenant.¹⁹ The extent of the duty of an ex-employee not to disclose confidential information is not entirely clear although it has been considered by the Courts on a number of occasions.²⁰ The most famous case in this respect perhaps is

¹⁶ *Wessex Dairies Ltd v Smith* (1935)2 K.B. 80

¹⁷ (1946)1 All ER 350, CA at 357

¹⁸ Morton LJ said: In all the circumstances of the case, have these five employees observed the obligations of good faith and fidelity? I do propose to recapitulate the facts, but I must start from this point, that the work done for the Defendants was done in what is usually described as the employees' spare time. No cases were cited to us in which work so done was held to be a breach of the employer. I do not propose to express any view of such a general nature as that all work done for a firm in the same line of business as the employers in the spare time of the employees is a breach of contract, but I do say that in my view the obligation of fidelity subsists so long as the contract of service subsists, and even in his spare time an employee does owe that obligation of fidelity.

¹⁹ Selwyn Norman, *Selwyn's Law of Employment* (5th edn. Butterworths, 1985) 323 See also *Faccenda Chicken Ltd v Fowler* (1986) I.R.L.R. 69

²⁰ D.W Crump, *Dix & Crump on Contracts of Employment* (6th edn. Butterworths, 1980)117

*ROBB v GREEN*²¹ where the Defendant was a manager of the plaintiff's business. Before he left his employment, he copied out lists of his employer's customers to enable him to approach those customers on behalf of the business which he intended to operate when the employment terminated. The court had no difficulty in deciding that the employee was obligated to the employer to keep good faith between them, and the employee had clearly contravened this duty by copying out the lists for his own use. Subject to these restrictions, an ex-employee is entitled to make use of his skill and knowledge which he has generally acquired in his previous employments.²²

It is worthy of note however, that under the common law there is nothing that will preclude a former employee from competing with his former employer, that is to say, under Common Law all covenants in restraint of trade are prima facie void. This position of the Common law was given judicial blessing in *NORDENFELT v MAXIM NORDENFELT GUNS AND AMMUNITION CO.*²³ The facts of the case were as follows; Thorsten Nordenfelt had established a valuable business in the manufacturing of machine guns, operating in Sweden and England. His customers included most national governments across the world. He sold the business to a company, which then transferred it to Maxim Nordenfelt. At that time Thorsten Nordenfelt entered into an agreement with Maxim that he (Thorsten) would not for a term of 25 years engage in the manufacture of guns, explosives, etc, other than on behalf of the company. Thorsten broke this covenant, alleging that it was unenforceable as being in restraint of trade.

The House of Lords affirmed the decision of the Court of Appeal that the covenant, though operating as a worldwide ban, was not wider than was necessary to protect the interests of Maxim Nordenfelt.

Lord Macnaghten stated the House's view of the correct approach to contracts of this type:

The public have an interest in every person carrying on his trade freely: so, has the individual. All interference with individual liberty of action in trading, and all restraints of trade of themselves, if there is nothing more, are contrary to public

²¹ (1895)2 QB 315

²² *United Sterling Corporation v Felton and Mannion* (1973) F.S.R 409

²³ (1894) A.C

policy, and therefore void. That is the general rule. But there are exceptions: restraints of trade and interference with individual liberty of action may be justified by the special circumstances of a particular case. It is a sufficient justification, and indeed it is the only justification, if the restriction is reasonable – reasonable, that is, in reference to the interests of the parties concerned and reasonable in reference to the interests of the public...²⁴

Where the employer has a legitimate interest to be protected, the law will however, protect such interest. When it comes to employment contracts, there are two legitimate interests requiring protection; trade secrets and highly confidential information on the one hand, goodwill and trade connections on the other hand.²⁵ An employer may seek to protect these interests by restraining the employee from engaging in a similar business at all, or by using what is known as a non-solicitation clause, i.e. prohibiting the employee from canvassing customers and possibly extending to prohibiting selling to, dealing with, or serving customers. The former is rather more draconian than the latter.²⁶ Examples from the cases where a restraint on an employee has been held to protect a legitimate interest include a hairdresser²⁷, a sales representative²⁸ and a tailor.²⁹ The courts have been prepared to recognize that the categories of legitimate interest are not closed. For example, in *GREIG v INSOLE*,³⁰ which concerned restrictions placed on professional cricketers by the cricketing authorities, Slade J recognized that there might be a public interest that the game of cricket should be properly organized and administered. On the facts, however, the restraint was in any case unreasonable. In *EASTHAM v NEWCASTLE UNITED FOOTBALL CLUB LTD*.³¹ However, Wilberforce J was unable to find a legitimate interest in relation to restrictions on freedom of transfer for professional footballers.³² It seems then that,

²⁴ Ibid at 565

²⁵ Titman & Camp (n 1)20

²⁶ Ibid

²⁷ *Marion White Ltd v Francis* [1972] 1 WLR 1423

²⁸ *Lucas (T) & Co Ltd v Mitchell* [1974] Ch 129; [1972] 3 All ER 689

²⁹ *Attwood v Lamont* [1920] 3 KB 571

³⁰ [1978] 3 All ER 449.

³¹ [1964] Ch 413; [1963] 3 All ER 139

³² This area (that is, football transfers) is one which has now been developed further by the influence of European Community law relating to competition and the free movement of workers: see the *Bosman* case – *Union Royale Belge des Sociétés de Football Association v Bosman* (Case C-415/93) [1995] ECR I-4921; [1996] 1 CMLR 645.

although in theory the categories of interest are open, the courts are likely to be very cautious in finding new interests.

Both types of clauses as stated above are capable of being valid as the courts have shown in a line of judicial authorities depending however on the reasonability in relation to time³³ and area of the restriction³⁴ and also the interest of the public will be considered. The case of *WYATT v KREGLINGER AND FERNAU*³⁵ shows the fact that public interest is an essential ingredient in the making of a contract in restraint of trade void.³⁶ The basis of this decision seems to be that if a contract did exist, it was supported only by an illegal consideration moving from Wyatt, i.e. an agreement not to engage in the wool trade. If he had been entitled to a pension as part of his original contract of service, then no doubt the pension arrangements would have been severed and enforced.³⁷ It will seem from decided cases however, that the rule is stricter in relation to indulging in similar businesses.³⁸ The reasonability or not of a restriction clause is a function left for the Courts to decide.³⁹ While a court may *alter* an unreasonable term or terms of a non-compete agreement, it also reserves the power to *invalidate* the agreement in totality if it is reasonably satisfied that the employer intentionally included overly broad language that renders it unreasonable and oppressive. In *MESOP KHOLOPIKIAAN v METAL FURNITURE NIGERIA LTD*,⁴⁰ a non-compete clause which covered a radius of 800 miles from Ikeja, Lagos where the

³³ In *M & S Drapers V Reynold (1956) 3 All ER 814*, a restraint on a collector's salesman of a drapery firm not to solicit his employer's clients for five years was voided on the ground that the restraint was too long in view of his humble position in the company. Similarly, in *Esso Petroleum Ltd v Harper's Garage (Stourport) Ltd (1967) UKHL 1*, the court voided a twenty-year restraint imposed on a petrol station owner under a *solus* agreement for being too unreasonably lengthy.

³⁴ *John Holt & Co (Liverpool) Ltd v Chalmers (1918) 3 NLR 77*

³⁵ (1933) 1 KB 793

³⁶ In June 1923, the Defendants wrote to the Plaintiff, who had been in their service for many years, intimating that upon his retirement they proposed to give him an annual pension of £200 subject to the condition that he did not compete against them in the wool trade. The Plaintiff's reply was lost and he did not appear ever to have agreed for his part not to engage in the wool trade, but he retired in the following September and received the pension until June 1932 when the Defendants refused to make any further payments. The plaintiff sued them for breach of contract. The Defendants denied any contract existed and also pleaded that if the contract existed, it was void as being in restraint of trade. The Court of Appeal gave judgment for the Defendants and although there was no unanimity with regard to the ratio decidendi, it appeared to two Judges that the contract was injurious to the interests of the public, since to restrain the plaintiff from engaging in the wool trade was to deprive the community of services from which it might derive advantage.

³⁷ Denis Keenan (n.1) 168

³⁸ See *Greer v Sketchy Ltd (1979) I.R.L.R. 445*; *Mason v Provident Clothing & Supply Co. Ltd (1913) A.C. 724*; *Contrast Spafax Ltd v Harrison (1980) I.R.L.R. 442*

³⁹ See *Commercial Plastics Ltd v Vincent (1965) 1 QB 623* Where the Plaintiff's claim failed solely because the restrictive covenant was too widely drawn as regards area

⁴⁰ (unreported) *HCL, Ikeja Judicial Division, Suit No IK/180/69 delivered on 5th March 1974*

defendant was based was held unreasonable and therefore void for it does not only span the whole of Nigeria but extends into some neighboring West African States.

The type of activity restrained must also be related to the interest being protected. A clause restraining someone who had been employed as a chiropodist from working as a hairdresser would be unlikely to be regarded as reasonable.⁴¹

At one time, the approach of the courts was to take clauses literally in assessing their reasonableness. Thus, if no area were specified, the restriction would be taken to be worldwide. The cases of *LITTLEWOODS v HARRIS*⁴² and *CLARKE v NEWLAND*⁴³ have suggested a different approach, requiring the restraint to be limited by the 'factual matrix' within which it was imposed.⁴⁴ In *Littlewoods v Harris*, an employee who had been employed solely in connection with the plaintiffs' mail order business was made subject to a restraint which, on its face, covered all aspects of the plaintiffs' wide ranging business activities. The Court of Appeal, however, held that the relevant clause should be interpreted as being intended only to apply to the mail order business in the UK. On that basis, it was reasonable. Similarly, in *Clarke v Newland*, a broad agreement by a doctor 'not to practice' was held to mean 'Practice as a general medical practitioner' (rather than, for example, in a hospital) since that was the role in which the defendant had previously been employed.

Basically, there are four elements a court will look at to determine if a trade secret or confidential information should be protected. This was succinctly stated by Sir Robert Megarry, V-C in the case of *THOMAS MARSHALL (Exports) Ltd v GUNLE*⁴⁵ thus;

If one turns from the authorities and looks at the matter as a question of principle, I think (and I say this very tentatively, because the principle has not been argued out) that four elements may be discerned which may be of some assistance in identifying confidential information or trade secrets which the court will protect. I speak of such information or secrets only in an industrial or trade setting. First, I think that the information must be information the release of

⁴¹ Contracts in Restraint of Trade [cw.routledge.com>textbooks>stone>c...](http://cw.routledge.com/textbooks/stone/c...) assessed on 22/5/2024

⁴² [1978] 1 All ER 1026

⁴³ [1991] 1 All ER 397

⁴⁴ This approach has recently been confirmed by the Court of Appeal in *Beckett Investment Group v Hall* [2007] EWCA Civ 613; [2007] ICR 1539.

⁴⁵ (1978) 3 All ER 193 209, ChD

which the owner believes would be injurious to him or of advantage to his rivals or others. Second, I think the owner must believe that the information is confidential or secret, i.e. that it is not already in the public domain. It may be that some or all of his rivals already have the information: but as long as the owner believes it to be confidential. I think he is entitled to try and protect it. Third, I think that the owner's belief under the two previous heads must be reasonable. Fourth, I think that the information must be judged in the light of the usage and practices of the particular industry or trade concerned. It may be that information which does not satisfy all these requirements may be entitled to protection as confidential information or trade secrets: but I think that any information which does satisfy must be of a type which is entitled to protection.

Most times in a bid to protect his trade secrets and confidential information, an employer since he cannot prevent an ex-employee from competing with him, nor from using the knowledge, skill and experience gained during employment can extract a promise that the ex-employee will not use his personal influence over customers, or his knowledge of trade secrets, to the disadvantage of the employer in as much as such signed promise is reasonably necessary for the protection of the employer's business. Thus, an employer who wishes to have protection against the disclosure of confidential information should get the employee to sign a covenant to this effect, so that the employee's future conduct is restricted once the employment comes to an end. Normally, this will be signed at the commencement of the employment, but though desirable, this is not essential.⁴⁶ In *R S COMPONENTS LTD v IRWIN*,⁴⁷ the employer asked a salesman, who was already employed, to sign a covenant which would have prevented him from soliciting business from the firm's customers for a period of twelve months after leaving the employment. The employee refused to do so, and his consequent dismissal was held by the NIRC to have been fair on the grounds of 'some other substantial reason'.

There are several limitations on the right of the employer to impose such restraints, for the courts will look with critical eye at any agreement which has the effect of restraining a person from earning his livelihood in the future. The employer cannot

⁴⁶ Selwyn Norman (n5)325

⁴⁷ (1973) IRLR 239

take away the employee's skill, experience and fund of knowledge which he has obtained during the employment, and, in particular, the employer cannot protect himself against future competition per se. This position was aptly captured in *STRANGE v MANN*⁴⁸ where the Defendant was employed by a firm of bookmakers as a manager. Most of the betting was done by telephone, and hence the Defendant had little personal contact with customers. He agreed that he would not, after leaving the employment, be engaged in a similar business within a radius of twelve miles. After leaving his job, he set up in business as a bookmaker within the prohibited area. It was held that the restriction was void. The purpose of the covenant was not to give legitimate protection to the business interests of the employer, but was a naked attempt to prevent future competition.

Furthermore, more often than not most of the employers rely on restrictive covenants in employment contracts to protect themselves from competition, however it is clear from judicial precedents that the right of an employee to employment is more important than safeguarding the interest of an employer. In **DESICCANT ROTORS INTERNATIONAL PVT. LTD v BAPPADITYA SARKAR AND ANOR**⁴⁹ it was held that "*It is this attempt to protect themselves from competition which clashes with the right of the employees to seek employment where so ever they choose and in a clash like this, it is clear that the right of livelihood of the latter must prevail.*"

It is also important to note that where a contract is declared void as being in restraint of trade, the rest of the contract remains valid and will be upheld. In other words, the void clause will be severed from the rest of the contract, see *ATTWOOD v LAMONT*⁵⁰. Additionally, where a restraint provision contains several distinct restraints, some of which are reasonable and some of which are not, the unreasonable elements will be severed and the rest of the provisions upheld.⁵¹ This is known as the blue pencil test.

5.0 RESTRICTIVE COVENANTS AND TRAINING BONDS

A lot of times, people tend to confuse training bonds and contracts in restraint of trade and for the purpose of clarity we shall discuss same. It is normal practice in the aviation

⁴⁸ (1965) 1 All ER 1069

⁴⁹ 2006(3) ARBLR118 (Delhi)

⁵⁰ (1920) 3KB 571

⁵¹ *Goldsoll v Goldman* (1915) 1 Ch 292

industry for airlines to sponsor their pilots' technical training. In order to recoup their investment, such airlines use training bonds which bind the sponsored pilots to remain in the service of the sponsor airline for a specified period, failing which they must repay the cost of the training. The validity and enforceability of such training bonds has been the subject of debate in employment law circles, especially in view of the recent amendment to the jurisdiction of the National Industrial Court (NIC) to include acts and practices which may constitute unfair labour practices. In *Overland v Captain Raymond Jam*, the NIC was faced with the question of whether a training bond could be enforced against a pilot who had changed employers and the consequence of the breach of training bonds.

Overland Airways Limited, an airline which specializes in commercial and charter flights, sued former employee Raymond Jam to recover the cost of sponsoring his training. The terms and conditions of the sponsorship had been outlined in two training bonds which required Jam to remain in Overland's employment for 36 months and 12 months, respectively. Jam had subsequently attended the training and acquired licenses and qualifications as a result. However, despite the terms of the training bonds, Jam resigned from his employment and repudiated the training bonds.

Jam argued that the training bonds were void and unenforceable because they constituted a restraint of trade and an unfair labour practice. Overland claimed that the training bonds were freely entered into by the parties and were necessary for the protection of its business interests. Overland further argued that training bonds are not contracts in restraint of trade and are enforceable in Nigeria and other jurisdictions. The NIC exercised its discretion to have recourse to international best practice and noted that in other jurisdictions – particularly India – training bonds are enforceable subject to the overriding condition of reasonableness. The NIC rejected Jam's contention that Overland's training bonds were at variance with the prevailing custom in the Nigerian aviation industry (in which pilots were allegedly bonded only for the validity period of their license) on the grounds of lack of evidence.

The NIC then considered the reasonableness of the bonds and held that the 36-month and 12-month periods for which Jam was bonded were reasonable in the circumstances. The bonding and repayment terms were also held to be reasonable and not an unfair labour practice (as contended by Jam). However, the NIC adopted the

practice of other jurisdictions wherein the amount that an employer is allowed to recover following a breach of a training bond is limited to the cost of the training pro-rated for the remainder of the bond period. Jam was therefore ordered to pay costs in accordance with this calculation.

6.0 RESTRAINT OF TRADE AND ARTISTIC FREEDOM

In relation to Artists and Brand Ambassadors especially those engaged by telecommunications companies in Nigeria, it is a known practice that such Brand Ambassadors are precluded from working with Ambassadors of rival brands even on projects that are not in competition.

Contracts or an agreement for brand ambassadorship in Nigeria come mostly in standard form in the sense that it has been sharpened by legal challenges, technological and marketing development.⁵² The exclusivity clause that forbids a particular brand ambassador in the telecommunications industry from having anything to do with rival brand ambassador is no doubt a violation of freedom of association and a partial restraint. The key point is not whether the artist has been restrained from plying his trade or business but whether both parties in the agreement are mutually committed to each other. It becomes unfair when one of the parties, usually the artist, is bound exclusively to a party who is not similarly bound.⁵³

The 1974 English House of Lords decision in *SCHROEDER MUSIC PUBLISHING COMPANY LIMITED v MACAULEY* is quite illustrative and helps to understand when an artist can be said to have been denied the right to ply his trade in the real sense. This case was the first musical contract in which the doctrine was applied. It involved a young and unknown song writer by name Macauley who entered into an agreement for exclusive services with a publishing company for five years. The song writer assigned to the publisher full and universal copyright in each of the original songs created at any time during the agreement. The publisher paid 50 pounds as a general advance against royalties and when the first 50 pounds was recouped from royalties, they would advance a further 50 pounds to be recouped again from royalties. The advances were to continue throughout the initial five-year period and could be

⁵² Rockson Igelige 'Restraint of Trade In Artists and Brand Ambassadors Contracts' *Premium Times* (Abuja, 6 April 2016)

⁵³ *Ibid*

extended if the total royalties advanced equaled or exceeded 50 pounds. The publisher could terminate with just one month written notice but the songwriter could not terminate the agreement. Besides, the Publisher was under no obligation to publish any of the songs and the songwriter could earn nothing if the works were not published.

The decision in *Schroeder v Macaulay* was applied in the similar case of *Clifford Davis Management Ltd v WEA Records Ltd*.⁵⁴ In *Panayiotou v Sony Music Entertainment (UK) Ltd*,⁵⁵ on the other hand, a recording contract which was probably in restraint of trade when entered into had been renegotiated after the performer concerned (George Michael) had become famous. His subsequent attempt to challenge the renegotiated agreement failed because, although it contained some unfavourable conditions, the performer had received full legal advice. Moreover, the renegotiated agreement was part of a settlement of the dispute of the original contract. In this context, public policy favoured giving effect to the settlement, and therefore the revised contract. In any case, the recording company had a legitimate interest to protect, in that it wished to sell as many records as possible, and the restrictions on the performer were not unreasonable as a means of protecting that interest.

7.0 RESTRICTIVE COVENANTS IN OTHER JURISDICTIONS

7.1 BELGIUM

In this jurisdiction, an employee under their employment contract must refrain from competing with his employer, since he is obliged to perform his contract in good faith. However, upon termination of this contract he is fully entitled to take up any activity whatsoever, either on an independent basis or under an employment contract concluded with a competing firm. He may waive this fundamental right by agreeing to have a non-competition clause inserted in the employment contract. The employee thereby undertakes not to engage in any similar activity – either on an independent basis or as an employee of a rival firm – whereby he could prejudice his former employer and put his industrial or commercial knowledge to use either for his personal

⁵⁴ [1975] 1 All ER 237.

⁵⁵ [1994] Ch 142; [1994] 1 All ER 755

benefit or to the advantage of his new employer. The non-competition covenant implicitly prohibits solicitation of and dealing with clients of the employer.

As a non-competition covenant restricts an employee's fundamental freedom to work, it will only be considered valid if certain strict legal conditions are met.

There are three types of non-competition clauses:

• **A general non-competition covenant**

The general non-competition covenant is only valid if inserted into the contract of an employee whose yearly gross remuneration exceeds EUR 64,508 (as of 1 January 2013). The clause must also:

- (i) relate to similar activities;
- (ii) be geographically restricted to the area where the employee could compete with his former employer (in any case, it cannot exceed the Belgian territory);
- (iii) be limited in time to a maximum period of twelve months as from the final day of the party's working relationship; and
- (iv) provide for a lump sum to be paid by the employer (unless it decides to waive the non-competition covenant within fifteen days of the end date of the contract): this compensation must equal to half of the employee's gross salary for the duration of the non-competition covenant.

The non-competition covenant will only be applicable if, after the end of the trial period, the employment contract is terminated:

- (v) by the employer on serious grounds;
- (vi) by the employee (upon provision of a notice period, or payment of a notice indemnity);
- (vii) by mutual consent; and
- (viii) upon expiry of the fixed term (in case of a contract concluded for a fixed duration of time) or upon completion of the specified job (in case of a contract concluded for a certain job).

An employee held to be in breach of the non-competition covenant will not only be obliged to reimburse the compensation he received from his employer but will also have to pay an additional indemnity equal to this amount. However, the judge may, at the employee's request, reduce the amount of this indemnity, taking into account the actual damage inflicted by the employee during the period of time when the covenant was not respected. Conversely, the judge may, at the employer's request, award a higher indemnity if the employer succeeds in proving that there has been damaged and is able to quantify the damage.

• **A specific non-competition covenant**

A specific non-competition covenant can only be inserted in employment contracts for white-collar employees of certain companies. It concerns companies that comply with one or both of the following conditions:

- (ix) companies which have an international field of operations or important economic, technical or financial interests on the international markets; or
- (x) companies which have their own research services.

In such companies, the specific non-competition clause can only be applied to the employees whose work allows them to acquire, directly or indirectly, knowledge or a practice peculiar to the enterprise, the use of which outside the enterprise could be prejudicial to it.

Under these conditions, it is possible to deviate from:

1. the maximum period of twelve months; and
2. the limitation to the national territory. Unlike the general covenant, this covenant can also apply during the trial period, or after the trial period in cases where there was a dismissal by the employer without serious cause.

• **Specific rules apply to sales representatives**

Specific rules apply to sales representatives. An employee will be considered a sales representative when their main function is to visit clients with a view of negotiating and/or concluding deals.

The conditions regarding the non-competition covenant for a sales representative differ slightly from the conditions mentioned above:

(i) the clause is valid if inserted into the contract of a sales representative whose annual gross remuneration exceeds EUR 32,254 (threshold as of 1 January 2013); (ii) the clause must not provide for a lump sum to be paid by the employer; (iii) the clause must not be restricted to Belgian territory but must be restricted to the specific area where the sales representative actually executes his activities.

A sales representative held to be in breach of the non-competition covenant will be obliged to pay an indemnity equal to three months remuneration.⁵⁶

7.2 UNITED KINGDOM

Post-termination restrictive covenants are fairly common in English employment contracts, particularly for senior employees or those with valuable connections, relationships or access to confidential information. However, post-termination restrictive covenants are unenforceable unless an employer can establish that:

- a. it has a legitimate business interest that it is seeking to protect; and
- b. the restriction goes no further than is reasonably necessary (in scope and duration) to protect that interest.

Legitimate business interests include trade secrets and confidential information, trade connections such as customers or suppliers, and maintaining the stability of the workforce.

Whether a restriction is reasonable is judged at the time the restriction is entered into. Relevant considerations will be the employee's role, duties and seniority, the nature of the employer's business, the scope of the restriction (such as what type of activity, trade connections or employees it covers, its geographical scope) and its duration (how long the restriction lasts). To a lesser extent, a court may also consider the length of the employee's notice period and, in some cases (but this not an established principle), what consideration the employee received. The most common remedy for breach of a

⁵⁶Mayer Brown A global guide to 'restrictive covenants' https://www.mayerbrown.com/files/uploads/Documents%5CGuide%20to%20Restrictive%20Covenants/MB_rest-cov_emea.pdf accessed on 4/3/2024

restrictive covenant is an injunction using the civil courts, to restrain the employee's or the new or prospective employer's activities, but other forms of injunction are available. Other remedies include damages for breach of contract and other forms of financial compensation.⁵⁷ In United Kingdom, an employer can only require a post-termination non-compete clause if such an employee agrees. To show that a legitimate interest exists to be protected, the terms of the restriction should not be onerous and should be primarily intended to protect confidential information and trade secrets. More recently, they have also been upheld where the employer can show that a narrower non-solicitation restriction was difficult to police.

In terms of drafting, it is particularly important to make sure that the scope and duration of the restriction is limited, bearing in mind the general principles mentioned above. Non-competition covenants sometimes apply for shorter periods than non-solicitation covenants. The time period of the restriction may also be reduced by any time the employee spends on garden leave (when he continues to be employed under the contract but he has no active duties or work to do).

It is worthy of note that unlike the case in Belgium and some other jurisdictions, there is no legal requirement to pay employees during the period of a post-termination restrictive covenant.

These restrictions can cover non-solicitation of, or non-dealing with, customers/clients. Solicitation tends to cover more active targeting of business. Non-dealing prevents the employee from accepting business from a customer even if they had not actively sought out that business. A non-dealing covenant is therefore more difficult to enforce, although it has been upheld where the employer can demonstrate that solicitation is hard to police, and is usually used together with a non-solicitation covenant. It is necessary for the employer to show a legitimate interest in having the covenant upheld. In the context of the contacts prohibition covenant, this interest is likely to be either a fear that the employee might misuse the influence the employee has over clients/customers which has been built up and paid for by the employer, or a concern about the misuse of the employer's confidential information being used to win business at the expense of the employer. These types of restrictions are often limited

⁵⁷ Ibid

to prohibiting contact with clients actually known to the employee or for whom he was responsible or had some involvement with in the course of his employment. They are usually defined by reference to a limited period of time before termination e.g. those he had contact with in the 6 or 12 months before termination.

Purely social contact is sometimes permitted, although that can make the restriction difficult to police in practice. In each case, the contact which is to be prohibited must have a business element to it, such as looking to compete with the ex-employers' business, or soliciting business in competition with the ex-employer. Prospective customers/clients can be included in this type of restriction but this would generally be limited to those that the employer was actively targeting prior to termination. Non-solicitation of employees' clauses agreed between the employee and employer have been upheld by the Court. However, it is usually assumed that it is not possible to prohibit the hiring of employees by a former employee. Most restrictions of this type will define the employees who cannot be approached or hired by reference to their seniority, grade or level, or their role in or importance to the business. They often only apply to colleagues that the departing employee had a reasonable level of contact with, knowledge of or responsibility for, and within a defined period before the departing employee leaves. Smaller companies may be able to enforce a restriction that covers a wider set of employees.

It is usually assumed that it is not possible to prohibit the hiring of employees by a former employee. Accordingly, in practice, it is difficult for employers to prove that a non-solicitation of employees' covenant has been broken, because merely showing that the employee has been hired by a former colleague is not necessarily a breach of the non-solicitation covenant. Therefore, non-solicitation of employee's covenants is generally the weakest type of covenant and the easiest to circumvent.

There are a variety of other restrictions that can apply during or after termination of employment. A common clause is to restrict the use or disclosure of confidential information and company property, during employment and after its termination. These tend to be defined types of information or property, although these definitions are often much wider than in other types of restrictions. They often do not have a set time limit after termination and instead apply for so long as the information retains its confidential nature. Other post-termination restrictions can cover non-solicitation

of or non-dealing with suppliers, distributors or intermediaries such as brokers, depending on the employer's business. These are similar to the customer/client restrictions mentioned above. Employees can be prevented from interfering with the ex-employer's business or connections, although this tends to require some kind of active attempt or intention to damage the ex-employer's business.

It is fairly common for restrictions which apply after termination to also be expressed to apply during employment. Restrictions during employment can, however, be wider and more onerous on the employee than those that apply after termination, because employees owe a higher level of duty to their existing employer.

Restrictive covenants are sometimes supplemented by provisions such as a requirement on an employee to inform their employer if they are aware of a raid on the employer's workforce (a team move), to alert the employer to another employee's wrongdoing or even to the employee's own wrongdoing, or to provide a prospective new employer with a copy of the restrictive covenants.

Employees can be restricted from holding themselves out as being connected to the ex-employer once they have left. They can be prevented from making disparaging statements about their ex-employer or its personnel.

Other restrictions may have an impact on an employee's ability to compete, although they are not restrictive covenants in the standard sense e.g. bad leaver provisions in a bonus plan which apply if an employee leaves and competes with his employer, or deferred compensation that is only payable if an employee does not compete for a period after he leaves employment. The general principles that apply to standard restrictive covenants can also apply to these types of indirect restriction.⁵⁸

In relation to the law that should govern a contract in restraint of trade, if English law applies to the contract, then it is very likely that the English law principles mentioned above will apply to the interpretation and enforcement of restrictive covenants. If another country's law applies to the contract but the English court has jurisdiction to hear the dispute, then the English court will generally apply that other country's law when interpreting the contract, but public policy considerations and mandatory

⁵⁸ Ibid

English law could override the interpretation or enforcement of the contract or impact the remedies available via the English court.

8.0 EFFECT OF BREACH OF CONTRACT

As regards employment contracts, restraints will be unenforceable if the contract, has been terminated following a repudiatory breach by the employer.⁵⁹ This does not mean, however, that a restrictive covenant contained in a contract which purports to make it enforceable after a repudiatory breach is therefore automatically unreasonable.⁶⁰ Thus, if the employee simply resigns, the restraint will be enforceable, provided it is otherwise reasonable according to the tests outlined above.

9.0 REMEDIES FOR BREACH OF RESTRICTIVE COVENANTS

If an employer has reason to believe that an employee has breached the post-termination restriction, the most common remedy sought is an injunction (or interdict in Scotland). An application will generally be made for an injunction and request that the employee "deliver up" or destroy confidential information. This means that the court will be asked to stop the employee in his tracks and will hear the full evidence at a later date in another trial.

Where an employer claims a financial remedy or damages for breach of a restrictive covenant in an employment contract, the employer will need to show some loss resulting from the breach. This will normally be loss of profits on contracts or opportunities diverted by the employee.

Where the employee has been induced by the employer's competitor into breaching restrictive covenants, the employer might choose to sue that competitor (particularly as the competitor company is likely to have greater financial resources from which to pay any award of damages made).

10.0 JURISDICTION

⁵⁹ *Rock Refrigeration Ltd v Jones* [1997] 1 All ER 1, applying *General Billposting Co Ltd v Atkinson* [1909] AC 118.

⁶⁰ *Ibid*

The National Industrial Court being a special Court created to handle matters arising from contracts of employment is in a better position to determine cases that have to do with contracts in restraint of trade in employment.

11.0 BURDEN OF PROOF

In employment cases arising from contracts in restraint of trade, the onus of showing that the restraint was reasonable rests on the person alleging it.

12.0 CONCLUSION

Intellectual property is undoubtedly one of the most invaluable assets in the intricate web that is the global business sphere, largely because of the time and resources expended in its contrivance. Hence the need to safeguard proprietary interest in trade secrets and confidential information from abuse by insiders becomes even more apparent by the day. This is why it is almost impossible to see a contemporary contract of employment devoid of a non-compete or confidentiality clause. Fortunately, a non-compete agreement, if painstakingly drafted, can obviate the dangers which it seeks to circumvent.

However, a small oversight can effectively vitiate a part or the entirety of the agreement to the detriment of the employer and the benefit of the employee and vice versa. Thus, it is suggested that when drafting a non-compete agreement, strict regard should be given to its scope, duration and enforceability. The agreement should be tailored to match the business and employee in contemplation and caution should be exercised in the reckless use of templates that are lifted verbatim from the internet. Better still, it would be prudent of an employer to outsource the drafting of non-compete agreements to a competent lawyer who is adequately versed in the art of corporate commercial legal drafting and handling contractual matters to ensure that the agreement is apposite, reasonable and fair.

From the foregoing, it is obvious that starting from Nigeria to Belgium and the United Kingdom, restrictive covenants are ordinarily made to protect the interest of the employer. However, the courts in an attempt to protect the employees have brought certain mechanisms to ensure that the employees are not left at the mercy of the employers. Therefore, it will be wrong to say strictly that restrictive covenants are aimed at protecting the employer alone.

Furthermore, from our study above it is our recommendation that express provisions should be made for restrictive covenants under Nigerian Employment Laws, and that also make the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission, (FCCPC) should also be made more effective just like in other jurisdictions to regulate this aspect of employment contracts in line with international best practices.